

Customers Attitude Towards Star Health Insurance in Tirupur City

Dr. M. Jayanthi

Assistant Professor, PG and Research Department of International Business,
Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts and Science, Nava India, Coimbatore – 641 006.

ORCID ID : 0009-0000-2361-7925

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.10686786

Abstract

An insurance policy protects against monetary loss. An insurance policy that covers all or a portion of a person's risk of having medical costs is known as health insurance. Because it offers a wide range of features and benefits to the general population, Star Health Insurance Company has become extremely popular among Indians among the numerous health insurance businesses. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine how customers feel about Star Health Insurance Company. 100 respondents in total were selected using the convenient random sample approach for a study conducted in Tirupur city. The majority of respondents (46%) preferred Star Health Insurance Company, according to the results.

Key Words: Customer, Star health, Insurance

Introduction

An insurance policy protects against monetary loss. It's a type of risk management that's mainly employed to protect against the possibility of an unforeseen or contingent loss. An insurer, insurance firm, insurance carrier, or underwriter is a business that offers insurance. An individual or organization that purchases insurance is referred to as a policyholder or insured. The insurance policy, which describes the terms and situations under which the insurer would pay the insured, is given to the insured. The premium is the sum of money that the insurer charges the policyholder for the coverage specified in the insurance policy. In the event that the insured suffers a loss that might be compensated by the insurance policy, the insured files

There are many different kinds of insurance available in our nation. Over the past ten years, health insurance has grown in popularity. Health insurance is a type of insurance that disperses the risk of a person's medical bills among a wide number of people by covering all or part of the risk. An insurer can create a regular financing structure, such as a payroll tax or monthly premium, to provide the funds necessary to pay for the health care benefits outlined in the insurance agreement by assessing the overall risk of medical spending and health system

costs over the risk pool. A central organization, such as a government agency, commercial enterprise, or non-profit organization, is responsible for overseeing the benefit. Med claim, a well-known term for health insurance in India, is

Public (government) health insurance: For some low-income individuals and families who fit certain criteria, public health insurance offers services and medical care. For central government personnel, these are comparable to the Central Government Health Scheme.

Private health insurance is a type of coverage that an individual owns and is not offered by their job or as part of a government-subsidized program. Star Health Insurance, Aviva Life Insurance, Munich Health Insurance Company Limited, Apollo Bajaj Allianz General Insurance Co Ltd, Family Health Plan Ltd, Reliance Health, Tata AIG, and other private health insurance companies are a few examples. (India, 2011) Star Health Insurance Company is one of the many health insurance providers that has gained a lot of popularity among Indians recently because it offers a number of features and advantages to the public

Star Health & Allied Insurance Company Limited:

For the fiscal year 2014–15, Star Health & Allied Insurance Company reported an incurred claim ratio of 63.96%. The organization handles cashless hospitalization facilities through an internal claim settlement process. In addition, Star Health & Allied insurance company develops a number of innovative solutions that provide HIV+ and diabetic patients with protection. With a focus on health insurance, personal accident, and overseas medical claim policies, Star Health and Allied Insurance Co Ltd launched its operations in 2006.

Products And Services:

- Family Health Optima Insurance Plan
- Senior Citizens Red Carpet Health Insurance Policy
- Star Comprehensive Insurance Policy
- Med-classic Insurance Policy
- Star Health Gain Insurance Policy
- Super Surplus Insurance Policy
- Diabetes Safe Insurance Policy
- Star Cardiac Care Insurance Policy

- Star Cancer Care Gold (Pilot Product)
- Star Net plus
- Star Micro Health Insurance
- Star Criticare Plus Insurance Policy
- Star Family Delite Insurance Policy
- Star Special Care
- Star Travel Protect Insurance Policy
- Star Corporate Travel Protect Insurance Policy
- Star Student Travel Protect Insurance Policy
- Accident Care Individual Insurance Policy
- Student Care

Statement Of the Problem:

Good health is vital to human life. Human well-being depends on having better health, yet there are numerous threats that can materialize at any time. Health insurance firms offer their services to protect people's lives. But with so many options accessible, it might be challenging to select the top health insurance provider in our nation. Because it offers a wide range of features and benefits to the general population, Star Health Insurance Company has grown to be quite popular among Indians among health insurance providers. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine how customers feel about the Star Health Insurance Policy.

Objectives Of the Study:

The following are the objectives of the study:

- To identify the factors which motivates the customers to take Star Health Insurance.
- To find out the customer's level of satisfaction towards Star Health Insurance.
- To offer valuable suggestions to increase the market potential of Star Health Insurance.

Research Methodology:

I. Research type – Descriptive research

II. Source of data – Primary data and Secondary data

III. Area of the study – Tirupur city

IV. Sampling design – Convenient random sampling method

V. Sample size – 100 respondents

VI. Period of study – December 2022 to January 2022.

TOOLS USED FOR ANALYSIS:

1. Percentage analysis
2. Mean scoring analysis
3. Simple ranking analysis

Limitations Of the Study:

The study's shortcomings are as follows: The respondent's answer might or might not be accurate. A few respondents declined to share the information because they were too busy or uninterested. The study's scope is restricted to Star Health Insurance Company general customers in Tirupur city; only 100 general customers' data were gathered owing to time constraints. If the study is carried out in a different geographic area, the outcomes may alter.

Analysis And Interpretation:

Coverage Of Employment For Medical Expenditure

S.NO	COVERAGE OF EMPLOYEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	No	56	56
2	Yes	44	44
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

As can be seen from the above table, of the total respondents surveyed for the study, 56% said that their employment does not cover all of their medical expenses, and 44% said that their employment does.

Majority (56%) of says that their employment does not cover their medical expenditure.

Most Preferred Insurance Company

S.No	NAME OF THE COMPANIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	Star Health Insurance Company	46	46
2	LIC	34	34
3	Reliance Health Insurance	14	14
4	United Indian Insurance	6	6
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

According to the above table, 46% of the total respondents surveyed for the study preferred Star Health Insurance, followed by LIC (34%), Reliance Health Insurance (14%), and United Indian Insurance (6%).

Majority (46%) of the respondents prefer Star Health Insurance Company.

Sources Influence the Respondents To Take Star Health Insurance

S.NO	FACTORS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	Spouse	28	28
2	Relation	26	26
3	Friends	20	20
4	Parents	14	14
5	Others	10	10
6	Internet	0	0
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

From the above table it is clear that out of total respondents taken for the study, 28% influenced by their Spouse, 26% influenced by their Relation, 20% of respondents influenced by friends to take Star Health, 14% influenced by their Parents and 10% influenced by Others like neighbors.

Majority (28%) of the respondents are influenced by their Spouse to take insurance in Star Health Insurance Company.

Satisfaction Level On Claim Settlements Of Star Health Insurance

S.NO	SATISFACTION LEVEL	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	Satisfied	68	68
2	Dissatisfied	16	16
3	Highly satisfied	12	12
4	Highly dissatisfied	4	4
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

The aforementioned table indicates that 68% of respondents are satisfied with Star Health Insurance settlements, 16% are dissatisfied with Star Health Insurance settlements, 12% are highly satisfied, and 4% are highly dissatisfied.

Majority (68%) of the respondents are satisfied with the claim settlements procedures of Star Health Insurance Company.

Factors Motivating The Respondents To Take Star Health Insurance

S.NO	PARTICULARS	RANK1	RANK 2	RANK3	RANK4	RANK5	TOTAL	MEAN	RANK
1	To protect from rising cost of healthcare	34	44	36	56	40	210	2.10	1
2	Tax benefits	30	40	60	80	40	250	2.50	2
3	Better healthcare for family	18	44	72	96	60	290	2.90	3
4	To cover big expenses	10	60	60	96	80	306	3.06	4
5	Expecting health problems	8	12	36	72	280	408	4.08	5

Source: Primary data

According to the above table, of the total number of respondents surveyed for the study, the factors "to protect from rising cost of healthcare" received the highest ranking, followed by "tax benefits" at rank 2, "better healthcare for family" at rank 3, "to cover big expenses" at rank 4, and "expecting health problems" at rank 5.

Majority of the respondents gave rank 1 ‘to protect from rising cost of healthcare’ which was considered as a main factor which motivates the customers to take Star Health Insurance.

Difficulties Faced By The Respondents Due To Star Health Insurance

S.NO	PARTICULARS	RANK1	RANK2	RANK3	RANK4	RANK5	TOTAL	MEAN SCORE	RANK
1	Poor service	22	44	9	132	100	307	3.07	4
2	Rate of premium	20	32	96	48	100	296	2.96	2
3	Terms and conditions stated by the company	20	56	48	96	60	280	2.80	1
4	Delay in claim settlement	26	32	60	100	80	298	2.98	3
5	Expected amount not sanctioned	5	40	90	40	155	330	3.30	5

Source: Primary data

From the above table out of total respondents taken for the study, respondents gave rank 1 for ‘terms and conditions stated by the company’, rank 2 for ‘rate of premium’, rank 3 for ‘delay in claim settlement’ and rank 4 for ‘poor service’ and rank 5 for ‘expected amount’ not sanctioned.

Majority of the respondents gave rank 1 for ‘terms and conditions stated by the star health insurance company’ as a major difficulty.

Findings Of The Study:

The following are the findings of the study:

- 1) Majority (50%) the respondents belong to the age group between 21-30years.

- 2) Majority (66%) of the respondents belong to Male.
- 3) Majority (40%) of the respondents are under graduates.
- 4) Majority (32%) of the respondents are self-employed.
- 5) Majority (30%) of respondents earns between Rs. 30001-40000.
- 6) Majority (56%) of says that their employment does not cover their medical expenditure.
- 7) Majority (46%) of the respondents prefer Star Health Insurance Company.
- 8) Majority (68%) of the respondents are satisfied with the claim settlements of Star Health Insurance Company.
- 9) Most (28%) of the respondents are influenced by their Spouse to take Star Health Insurance.
- 10) Majority of the respondents gave rank 1 'to protect from rising cost of healthcare which was considered as a main factor which motivates the customers to take Star Health Insurance Policy
- 11) Majority of the respondents gave rank 1 for 'terms and conditions stated by the Star health insurance' as a major difficulty.

Suggestions:

- Increasing public awareness about health insurance using various TV, social media, expo, trade show, and seminar advertisements.
- Robust underwriting and effective claims handling.
- Examine medical claims to see if "existing illness" coverage can be obtained, even at a higher cost.
- Instead of tapping into the same market, agents and private players could focus on new markets in rural and semi-urban areas. The penetration of health insurance will rise as a result.
- Thorough market research and the launch of new products are done by evaluating the target market, consumer demands, product potential, price strategy, and other factors.
- Star Health Insurance should promptly take appropriate measures to streamline the claim settlement process and expedite the compensation amount.
- The government tax should not be reflected in any premium prices.

Conclusion:

Customer awareness, which is often defined as when a product or service meets a customer's expectations, is the sentiment or attitude a customer has toward it after using it. The goal of the study is to examine how the Tirupur region's customers feel about Star Health Insurance Company. The primary goals of the research are to ascertain the variables that impact policyholders' knowledge of medical claim insurance products and the challenges they encounter. Furthermore, the majority of respondents were found to be aware of Star Health Insurance. The health insurance industry's mantra ought to be "health coverage to all." Healthcare facilities should be easily accessible, and cost-control measures ought to be implemented. Star Health Insurance must take various promotional measures explaining the benefits of their policy. Instead of concentrating more on profit, Star Health service should provide personalized service to its customers and due to it the Star Health Insurance will reach new heights in the near future and Mother India will be definitely, the healthiest nation in the world.

References

- Jayasubramanian,P, Dr (2022), A study on policy holder challenges and satisfaction towards Star health insurance during Covid period, International Journal of Creative Research thoughts, July, pp. 641 – 655
- Kshitij Patukle., (2013), Mediclaim and Health Insurance, Ocean Books Pvt. Ltd.
- Kothair C.R. (2004), Research Methodology, New Age International
- Rana Rohit Singh, Dr and Abhishek Sing, International Journal of Management, IT & Engineering, Vol. 10, Issue 04, April 2020

Cite this article

Jayanthi M “**Customers Attitude Towards Star Health Insurance in Tirupur City**” Scholastic Bazillion: Journal Of Multidisciplinary Studies, Vol.1, Issue 1, January 2024, pp. 1-9